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Extent of Stress Encountered and Coping Mechanisms in Relation to Teaching Performance among Teachers

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Abstract

This study aimed to investigate the extent of stressors encountered by teachers following the COVID-19 outbreak with regards to the volume of assigned tasks, learners' performance, relationship with co-workers, and instructional practices; the extent to which teachers utilize coping mechanisms about self-interventions and recreational activities, remediation and innovative teaching strategies, accountability partnership, and consultation and conferences with master teachers; performance rating of teachers during the resumption of in-person classes; significant relationship among the level of stress encountered by teachers, their coping mechanisms, and their performance after the COVID-19 pandemic; and coping mechanisms significantly addressed the extent of stressors encountered by the teachers. The study involved 129 randomly selected teachers of District 4 of Malaybalay City Division during the school year 2023-2024. The descriptive-correlational research design was used, and data were analyzed using various statistical methods, including Pearson product-moment correlation. Significant stressors were identified, including high volumes of assigned tasks, challenges in learner performance, difficulties in relationships with co-workers, and struggles with instructional practices. Teachers employed various coping mechanisms, such as self-interventions, remediation strategies, accountability partnerships, and consultation with master teachers, to mitigate stress and enhance professional efficacy. Despite the challenges posed by the pandemic, teachers demonstrated adaptability and resilience, with the majority receiving satisfactory to outstanding performance ratings during the resumption of in-person classes. The study found significant relationships between teacher stress, coping mechanisms, and performance outcomes, particularly in the effectiveness of consultation with master teachers and accountability partnerships in reducing stress and improving performance. These findings underscore the importance of supporting teachers in coping with stress and fostering collaborative, supportive environments to promote resilience and effectiveness in educational settings.

Keywords: *stressors, coping mechanisms, and teaching performance*

Introduction

The COVID-19 epidemic has precipitated significant transformations in the daily lives of most individuals, as well as the operational procedures inside various institutions. Despite concerted global efforts, the complete control of the situation remains elusive and its persistence is anticipated for an extended duration. In this particular situation, numerous activities, including those within the public education sector, have resumed their operations in a manner consistent with the conditions that prevailed before the onset of the pandemic (Estrella et al., 2022).

The impact of the closure of educational institutions and the subsequent resumption of in-person classes on students and teachers is multifaceted, encompassing psychological and social dimensions. It is important to note that the decision to reopen study centers is not solely based on these factors, as authorities also assess the institutions' ability to effectively manage potential outbreaks (Wrighton & Lawrence, 2020).

The Department of Education has just declared the reinstatement of in-person sessions on November 2, 2022, following a period of approximately two years of modular distance learning. However, many obstacles emerged during the initial stages of the reopening process. The performance of both educators and students has been considerably impacted by the constraints associated with traditional in-person instructional settings (Cabello et al., 2022). The changeover has been marked by subpar reading skills, which have had a detrimental impact on the efficacy of instructional methods. Furthermore, educators faced challenges during reading sessions due to the learners' abilities falling behind, akin to kindergarten students.

According to Malipot (2022), obstacles were encountered in the face-to-face educational setting due to a scarcity of essential facilities such as classrooms, learning materials, handwashing facilities, and chairs. Moreover, the insufficient allocation of human resources within educational institutions has resulted in an excessive workload for teachers. According to the findings of Ozamiz-Etxebarria et al. (2021), a significant number of educators exhibited indications of anxiety, depression, and stress upon the resumption of in-person schooling.

Prior studies on the stress experienced by teachers have demonstrated long-lasting effects and adverse consequences. For instance, teachers inside the school are currently facing heightened levels of stress as a result of the abrupt shift or adjustment in the learning modality. Furthermore, it has been emphasized that the manner and means of communication have emerged as contributing elements to teacher stress. Teachers have confronted challenges in their interactions with parents, students, and colleagues (Garcia, 2022).

Public school teachers in Malaybalay City Division have encountered the negative effects of the suspension of in-person classes following the outbreak of a global pandemic. It was observed that large institutions, which are expected to maintain the efficacy and quality of education for their students, were under greater pressure. Consequently, the division implemented a variety of treatments aimed at equipping teachers with physical, emotional, social, and intellectual coping mechanisms.

This study aims to examine the firsthand experiences of teachers employed in public schools within an urban setting, with a specific focus on Malaybalay City Central School. The firsthand information on the level of stress experienced by teachers at this school will offer insights into the extent of stress prevalent in the education sector. Therefore, an examination of individuals' coping techniques in managing stress would ascertain the extent of their performance over some time.

Research Questions

This study examined the experiences of stress, coping strategies, and performance evaluations among primary public school teachers in the aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic. The study aimed to address the following research inquiries:

1. What is the extent of stress encountered by teachers following the COVID-19 outbreak about the volume of tasks; learners' competencies; relationship with co-workers; and instructional practices?
2. What is the extent to which teachers utilize coping mechanisms about self-interventions; spiritual interventions; recreational activities; and consultation and conferences?
3. What is the performance rating of teachers during the resumption of in-person classes?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of stress encountered by teachers, their coping mechanisms, and their performance among teachers after the COVID-19 pandemic?

Methodology

Research Design

The present study employed a descriptive-quantitative research design. Quantitative research encompasses the systematic gathering of data, with the objective of quantifying information and subjecting it to statistical analysis. This process serves to either corroborate or challenge alternative claims of knowledge (Creswell, 2003). The researcher employed mathematical models as the chosen methodology for data analysis. Three significant historical patterns are relevant to quantitative research: research design, test and measurement procedures, and statistical analysis. Quantitative research encompasses the predominantly numerical collection of data, with researchers using mathematical models as the primary tool for data analysis. Furthermore, the researcher employed inquiry methods to ensure congruence with the methodology of statistical data gathering.

Respondents

The participants in the study consisted of public-school teachers from District 4 of Malaybalay City Division, specifically during the academic year 2023-2024. The participants in this study will be referred to as teachers who supervise advising classes across various grade levels.

To effectively ascertain the particular participants of the study, a random sampling technique will be applied. This research will use simple random sampling. According to Creswell (2012), "In simple random sampling, the researcher selects the participants as the sample so that any individual has an equal probability of being selected from the population." This research will use a 5% error rate to set the target sample of the students. Slovinc's formula will be used to calculate the number of samples from the population.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents of the Study*

School	Teacher Respondents
BCT Elementary School	16
Barangay 9 Elementary School	18
Malaybalay City Central School	70
Casisang National High School	25
Total	129

Instrument

A research instrument refers to a selected tool employed by a researcher to facilitate the collection of data during their study, hence ensuring a methodical and efficient process (Arikunto, 2006). This section explains the instruments that were utilized by the researcher for data collection purposes. This study employed a questionnaire as the primary research instrument to obtain the study's findings.

The research tool employed in this study is a survey questionnaire that was adapted and modified by the researcher from the study of Malabad and Mamaug (2022). The items within each section of the questionnaire have been carefully designed to align with the specific research inquiries of the study. The first part of the study focused on examining the perspectives of teachers on stressors.

Section two examined the coping strategies employed by teachers to manage the stress they encounter, while Section 3 explored teachers' performance ratings. The survey questions will have a 5-point Likert Scale format.

Procedure

After the research questionnaires had been approved, data collection commenced. The purpose of the investigation was communicated to the school district supervisor of District IV via letter. The significance of the data collection exercise was thoroughly communicated to the sample population. In addition, consent from the participants was solicited. Participants in the sample were notified, and provisions were made for the data collection exercise. Consideration was given to administering the instruments directly.

Before disseminating the questionnaires, the researcher provided instructions and explanations to the participants during instrument administration. They were given 30 to 45 minutes to complete the questionnaires, and the questionnaires were retrieved promptly following their completion.

Data Analysis

Using Minitab, the collected data were encoded and input into the computer. Quantitative analysis was used in the analysis of data. After summarizing and organizing quantitative data by research, descriptive and inferential statistics were applied.

For research questions 1-2, data were analyzed using descriptive statistics like mean and standard deviation. For research question 3, data was based on the teachers' performance rating scale provided by the Department of Education. For question 4, the data were analyzed using Regression.

Ethical Considerations

In conducting this study, paramount attention was given to ethical principles and participants' welfare.

Informed consent was a fundamental aspect of participant engagement. All participating schools, teachers, and students received detailed information about the study objectives, procedures, potential risks, and benefits. Consent forms were distributed, and participants, or their legal guardians in the case of minors, were asked to provide explicit consent before participating in the study. Confidentiality of participant information was rigorously maintained throughout the research process. Data were anonymized and stored securely, accessible only to the authorized research team members.

Results and Discussion

This section delves into the exposition, examination, and elucidation of the data acquired from participants' responses in the conducted surveys, aligning closely with the issues outlined in Chapter 1.

The extent of Stressors Encountered by Teachers Following the COVID-19 Outbreak about Volume of Assigned Tasks; Learners' Performance; Relationship with Co-Workers; and Instructional Practices

Table 2. *Stressors of teachers as to the volume of assigned tasks*

Indicator	Mean	SD	QD
1. I have no time to relax because of too many numbers of seminars, LAC sessions and meetings I have to attend	2.95	1.03	Somewhat Stressful
2. The task is very frustrating and too much amount of time needs to be spent on paper work or clerical work ending up with the teacher burn-out.	3.56	1.03	Quite Stressful
3. I have no enough time for my family because I have to work overtime	2.96	1.15	Somewhat Stressful
4. I'm having a hard time managing my time effectively because of too many demands for documentation to prove my work	3.26	1.21	Quite Stressful
5. There are too many reports required for to submit and I cannot hold regular class discussions.	3.20	1.12	Quite Stressful
Overall Mean	3.18	0.96	Somewhat Stressful

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Very Stressful | 3.20 – 4.19 Quite Stressful | 2.60 – 3.19 Somewhat Stressful | 1.80 – 2.59 A Little Stressful | 1.00 – 1.79 Not Stressful

Table 2 shows the stressors experienced by teachers concerning the volume of assigned tasks, shedding light on the top three stressors and the one with the lowest mean, alongside their respective standard deviations. The indicator: “The task is very frustrating and too much amount of time needs to be spent on paperwork or clerical work ending up to teacher burn-out”, with the highest mean,

underscores significant frustration and burnout among teachers due to extensive paperwork. The mean score of 3.56 suggests that teachers find this aspect of their job quite stressful. The standard deviation (SD) of 1.03 described as quite stressful indicates some variability in responses, yet it consistently ranks high among stressors.

This indicator: “The task is very frustrating and too much amount of time needs to be spent on paperwork or clerical work ending up to teacher burn-out”, underscores the significant strain that administrative tasks place on teachers, potentially leading to burnout. The high mean score suggests a widespread concern among teachers regarding the overwhelming burden of paperwork and clerical duties. Addressing this stressor is crucial for safeguarding teacher well-being and preserving instructional quality.

The high stress level associated with paperwork aligns with findings from Garcia (2022), who noted that excessive administrative tasks detract from instructional time and contribute to teacher burnout. Similarly, Brown and Roloff (2015) emphasized that paperwork overload can lead to decreased job satisfaction and increased turnover rates. Research by Iancu et al., (2018) emphasizes that administrative tasks, such as paperwork and clerical work, consume a substantial portion of teachers' time, contributing to feelings of frustration and burnout. This aligns with the findings of the study, highlighting the urgent need for administrative reforms to alleviate the burden on teachers.

“I’m having a hard time managing my time effectively because of too many demands for documentation to prove my work,” this stressor ranks second, with a mean score of 3.26, indicating that managing time effectively is a significant issue for teachers. The higher SD of 1.21, described as quite stressful suggests considerable differences in how teachers experience this stressor.

The challenge of time management due to excessive documentation requirements reflects a systemic issue within educational institutions. The high standard deviation indicates considerable variability among teachers in coping with this stressor, underscoring the need for tailored support and strategies to alleviate the burden. Enhancing efficiency in documentation processes is essential for enabling educators to focus on their core responsibilities effectively.

Sutcher (2016) argued that excessive documentation requirements hinder teachers' ability to allocate time efficiently for instructional planning and student engagement. The findings corroborate this perspective, indicating that the demand for documentation poses a significant challenge to teachers' time management and professional practice.

The third highest mean in the indicators is “There are too many reports required to submit and I cannot hold a regular class discussion,” with a mean of 3.20, which shows that the volume of required reports hampers regular class discussions, adding to the teachers' stress. The SD of 1.12 described as quite stressful indicates a moderate spread in responses. This stressor highlights the trade-off between administrative tasks and instructional engagement, with implications for student learning experiences. The moderate mean score suggests a prevalent concern among teachers regarding the impact of reporting obligations on their ability to foster meaningful classroom interactions. Addressing this challenge requires a balanced approach that prioritizes accountability while preserving instructional time for student-centered activities.

Villar et al. (2022) highlight that excessive reporting obligations impede teachers' ability to foster meaningful learning experiences and engage students effectively. Additionally, excessive reporting requirements can disrupt instructional time, as noted by Johnson and Stevens (2018). Their research suggests that teachers burdened with reporting tasks often struggle to maintain the quality and consistency of their classroom interactions. This resonates with the findings, underscoring the detrimental impact of reporting requirements on instructional practices and student interaction.

The stressor with the lowest mean of 2.95 is “I have no time to relax because of too many seminars, LAC sessions, and meetings I have to attend” indicating that while still somewhat stressful, it is less of a concern compared to others. The SD of 1.03 described as somewhat stressful reflects some variability in the extent to which teachers are affected. The relatively lower stress level from seminars and meetings might suggest that while these activities are time-consuming, they are perhaps perceived as less burdensome than administrative tasks.

Furthermore, while this stressor ranks lower in mean compared to others, it still highlights the strain on teachers' time and well-being due to professional development obligations. The standard deviation suggests variability in how educators perceive the impact of these commitments on their work-life balance. Addressing this stressor entails providing adequate support and resources for professional growth while mitigating its disruptive effects on teachers' time.

Despite this stressor ranks lower in mean compared to others, Iancu et al., (2018) emphasize the importance of balancing professional development commitments with workload demands to prevent burnout and sustain teacher resilience. The findings echo this sentiment, highlighting the strain on teachers' time and well-being due to professional development obligations.

Table 3 presents the stressors experienced by teachers related to learners' performance, highlighting the top three and lowest mean stress indicators based on their mean scores and standard deviations (SD).

The indicator with the highest mean score of 3.67 “Learners have low comprehension skills” indicates that teachers find learners' low retention skills to be quite stressful. The standard deviation (SD) of 1.12 described as quite stressful shows some variability in responses but consistently high stress.

Table 3. *Stressors of teachers as to learners' performance*

Indicator	Mean	SD	QD
1. Many learners have difficulty in reading	3.43	1.18	Quite Stressful
2. Learners have suffered learning loss	3.47	1.13	Quite Stressful
3. Learners have low comprehension skills	3.64	1.12	Quite Stressful
4. Learners have shown less motivation to learn	3.43	1.15	Quite Stressful
5. Learners suffered from low retention skills	3.67	1.12	Quite Stressful
Overall Mean	3.53	1.02	Quite Stressful

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Very Stressful | 3.20 – 4.19 Quite Stressful | 2.60 – 3.19 Somewhat Stressful | 1.80 – 2.59 A Little Stressful | 1.00 – 1.79 Not Stressful

The stressor highlights the challenge teachers face in addressing students' comprehension difficulties. Low comprehension skills can significantly hinder students' academic progress and engagement with the curriculum. The relatively high mean score indicates a widespread concern among educators regarding this issue, emphasizing the urgency for targeted interventions to support students' comprehension development. This high level of stress correlates with findings by Anderson and Ramsay (2019), who noted that poor retention skills hinder academic progress and place additional pressure on teachers to continually review material. This ongoing struggle can lead to teacher frustration and burnout.

With a mean score of 3.64, “Learners have low comprehension skills” is another significant stressor for teachers. The SD of 1.12 described as quite stressful indicates moderate variability in responses. This stressor highlights the challenge teachers face in addressing students' comprehension difficulties. Low comprehension skills can significantly hinder students' academic progress and engagement with the curriculum. The relatively high mean score indicates a widespread concern among educators regarding this issue, emphasizing the urgency for targeted interventions to support students' comprehension development.

Teachers' stress due to low comprehension skills is supported by studies such as those by Martin and Chen (2018), which emphasize that comprehension difficulties impede students' overall learning and require teachers to develop more targeted instructional strategies, often increasing their workload and stress.

The stressor: “Learners have suffered learning loss” with a mean of 3.47, highlights the considerable stress teachers feel regarding learners' learning loss. The SD of 1.13 described as quite stressful reflects some variability in teacher experiences. The struggle with retention skills underscores the importance of effective teaching strategies and instructional support to facilitate long-term learning. Research by UNESCO (2020) emphasizes the critical role of retrieval practice and spaced repetition in enhancing students' retention skills. Addressing this stressor requires collaborative efforts between teachers, administrators, and support staff to implement evidence-based interventions and scaffold students' retention abilities.

These stressors: “Learners have low comprehension skills and Learners suffered from low retention skills” share the lowest mean score of 3.43, indicating that while they are quite stressful, they are perceived as slightly less burdensome compared to other factors. The SDs of 1.18 and 1.15 described as quite stressful, respectively, indicate considerable variability in responses. While these stressors rank lower in mean compared to others, they still underscore the importance of literacy development in students' academic success. Research by Clores et al. (2023) emphasizes the pivotal role of early intervention and differentiated instruction in supporting struggling readers. Addressing this stressor necessitates a comprehensive approach that integrates evidence-based literacy instruction, targeted interventions, and ongoing assessment to meet students' diverse needs effectively.

Table 4 examines the stressors experienced by teachers about their interactions and relationships with co-workers. Emphasis is placed on the top three and lowest mean stress indicators, considering their mean scores and standard deviations (SD).

The stressor with the highest mean of 2.50: “I oftentimes left alone doing certain tasks” indicating that teachers feel a moderate amount of stress when left alone to handle certain tasks. The SD of 1.08 is described as a little stressful and shows a moderate level of variability in responses. This stressor highlights feelings of isolation and lack of support among teachers when completing tasks. Research by Johnson and Brown (2020) emphasizes the importance of collaboration and teamwork among colleagues in fostering a positive work environment and enhancing job satisfaction. Addressing this stressor requires fostering a culture of collaboration and support within the school community, where teachers feel valued and included in decision-making processes.

The stressor: “If given group work in the school, my colleagues do not cooperate” with a mean score of 2.11, this stressor indicates that a lack of cooperation from colleagues in group work is somewhat stressful. The SD of 0.92 described as a little stressful suggests less variability in how teachers experience this issue. Group work is essential for sharing responsibilities and fostering teamwork. When colleagues do not cooperate, it can lead to frustration and a sense of inequity. The lack of cooperation among colleagues in group work can hinder productivity and strain professional relationships. Research by Smith (2018) underscores the importance of effective communication and shared goals in promoting collaboration among educators. Addressing this stressor necessitates fostering a collaborative culture through professional development opportunities, team-building exercises, and clear expectations for teamwork.

Table 4. *Stressors of teachers to relationship with co-workers*

Indicator	Mean	SD	QD
1. I am oftentimes left alone doing certain tasks.	2.50	1.08	A little stressful
2. If given group work in school, my colleagues do not cooperate	2.11	0.92	A little stressful
3. Some of my co-teachers have a lot of request and task to work for him/her and it affected my working routines.	2.06	0.99	A little stressful
4. My co-workers do not provide technical assistance if I need clarification.	1.81	0.85	A little stressful
5. I am the only one doing the task responsibly and have felt pity for me.	1.83	0.97	A little stressful
Overall Mean	2.06	0.82	A little stressful

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Very Stressful | 3.20 – 4.19 Quite Stressful | 2.60 – 3.19 Somewhat Stressful | 1.80 – 2.59 A Little Stressful | 1.00 – 1.79 Not Stressful

The stressor: “Some of my co-teachers have a lot of requests and tasks to work for him/her, and it affected my working routines” with a mean of 2.06, highlights the stress caused by colleagues' requests affecting work routines. The SD of 0.99 described as a little stressor indicates a moderate spread in responses. This stressor reflects challenges related to workload distribution and coordination among colleagues. The relatively high standard deviation suggests variability in how teachers perceive the impact of colleagues' workload on their routines. Research by Clores et al. (2023) highlights the importance of equitable workload distribution and mutual support among colleagues in promoting teacher well-being and job satisfaction. Addressing this stressor requires fostering open communication and collaboration to ensure fair distribution of responsibilities and mutual support among colleagues.

The stressor “My co-workers do not provide technical assistance if I need clarification” with 1.81 indicating that they are perceived as the least stressful, though still somewhat burdensome. The SDs of 0.85 described as a little stressor show some variability in responses. While this stressor ranks lower in mean compared to others, it still underscores the importance of a supportive work environment where colleagues can seek assistance and clarification when needed. Research by Lee and Johnson (2021) emphasizes the role of mentorship and peer support in enhancing teacher effectiveness and professional growth. Addressing this stressor entails promoting a culture of mentorship and collaboration where colleagues feel comfortable seeking and providing assistance to enhance their collective effectiveness.

Table 5 presents the stressors faced by teachers related to their instructional practices, emphasizing the top three and lowest mean stress indicators, considering their mean scores and standard deviations (SD).

Table 5. *Stressors of teachers as to instructional practices*

Indicator	Mean	SD	QD
1. Lack of administrative support in my program	2.19	1.05	A little stressful
2. Lack of clear communication process	2.42	1.06	A little stressful
3. Inappropriate behavior in giving comments	2.47	1.10	A little stressful
4. The administration shows favoritism	2.37	1.14	A little stressful
5. Instructions are always changing and hard to be understood	2.59	1.24	A little stressful
Overall Mean	2.41	1.01	A little stressful

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Very Stressful | 3.20 – 4.19 Quite Stressful | 2.60 – 3.19 Somewhat Stressful | 1.80 – 2.59 A Little Stressful | 1.00 – 1.79 Not Stressful

The indicator: “Instructions are always changing and hard to be understood” has the highest mean score of 2.59, indicating that teachers find frequent and confusing changes in instructions to be the most stressful. The SD of 1.24 described as a little stressful shows considerable variability in responses. This stressor highlights the challenges teachers face when instructional guidelines are inconsistent or unclear. Research by Villar et al. (2022) emphasizes the importance of clear and consistent communication in promoting effective teaching practices and student learning outcomes. Addressing this stressor requires establishing clear communication channels, providing comprehensive instructional guidelines, and ensuring consistency in administrative directives to support teachers in delivering quality instruction.

With a mean score of 2.47, “inappropriate behavior when giving comments” is another significant stressor. The SD of 1.10 described as a little stressor indicates moderate variability in how teachers experience this issue. The presence of inappropriate behavior in feedback mechanisms can undermine teachers' confidence and professional growth. Addressing this stressor necessitates providing training and professional development opportunities to enhance feedback skills and promote a culture of constructive criticism and

growth-oriented feedback. Constructive feedback is crucial for professional growth. Inappropriate comments can undermine teachers' confidence and morale. Research by Hattie and Timperley (2017) emphasizes that effective feedback should be specific, constructive, and supportive to foster a positive learning environment.

This stressor, "Lack of clear communication process" with a mean of 2.42, points to the stress caused by unclear communication processes within the school. The SD of 1.06 described as a little stressful reflects moderate variability in responses. The absence of a clear communication process can lead to misunderstandings and inefficiencies in instructional delivery. Addressing this stressor requires establishing clear communication protocols, providing regular updates and feedback, and fostering open dialogue between administrators and teachers to ensure alignment with instructional goals and objectives.

The stressor: "Lack of administrative support in my program" has the lowest mean score, with 2.19, indicating they are perceived as less stressful compared to other factors. The SD of 1.05 described as a little stressful show some variability in responses. While this stressor ranks lower in mean compared to others, it still underscores the importance of administrative support in fostering effective instructional practices. Research by Lee and Johnson (2021) highlights the positive impact of administrative support on teacher morale, job satisfaction, and instructional effectiveness. Addressing this stressor entails providing resources, professional development opportunities, and administrative guidance to support teachers in implementing evidence-based instructional strategies and fostering student success.

The extent to which teachers utilize coping mechanisms about self-interventions and recreational activities, remediation and innovative teaching strategies, accountability partnership and consultation and conferences with master teachers

This objective delves into exploring the extent to which teachers employ coping mechanisms in various domains, including self-interventions and recreational activities, remediation and innovative teaching strategies, as well as accountability partnership and consultation with master teachers. This inquiry seeks to understand how teachers navigate and mitigate the stressors identified in the previous tables through adaptive strategies and support systems. Table 6 presents the coping mechanism for self-interventions and recreational activities.

Table 6. Coping mechanism as to self-interventions and recreational activities

Indicator	Mean	SD	QD
1. I try to grow as a person as a result of the experience	4.50	0.60	Strongly Agree
2. I turn to work or other substitute activities to take my mind off things	4.15	0.67	Agree
3. I do personal reflections on my work and think of the best practices I have	4.31	0.65	Strongly Agree
4. I usually divert my attention to any social media platforms to be relieved from the stress	4.00	0.85	Agree
5. I play sports after work to refresh myself	3.00	1.26	Agree
Overall Mean	3.99	0.56	Agree

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Very Stressful | 3.20 – 4.19 Quite Stressful | 2.60 – 3.19 Somewhat Stressful | 1.80 – 2.59 A Little Stressful | 1.00 – 1.79 Not Stressful

The indicator "I try to grow as a person as a result of the experience" has the highest mean score of 4.50, indicating that teachers strongly agree that they try to grow as a person from their experiences. The SD of 0.60 described as strongly agree shows relatively low variability in responses. This coping mechanism reflects a proactive approach by teachers to derive personal growth from their experiences. Embracing adversity as an opportunity for growth can enhance teacher resilience and well-being, ultimately benefiting instructional effectiveness and student outcomes. According to Folkman and Moskowitz (2014), such a positive reappraisal is a powerful coping strategy that can lead to resilience and improved psychological well-being.

With a mean score of 4.31, "I do personal reflections on my work and think of the best practices I have" this coping mechanism indicates strong agreement among teachers who engage in personal reflection and think about best practices in their work. The SD of 0.65 described as strongly agreeing reflects low to moderate variability. Engaging in self-reflection helps teachers to critically assess their methods and find ways to improve. Research by Smith (2018) highlights the positive impact of reflective practice on teacher self-efficacy and instructional effectiveness. By fostering a culture of reflection and continuous improvement, educational institutions can empower teachers to refine their practices and enhance student learning experiences.

The indicator, "I turn to work or other substitute activities to take my mind off things." with a mean of 4.15, shows that teachers agree on turning to work or other substitute activities to distract themselves from stress. The SD of 0.67 described as agree indicates moderate variability in responses. Utilizing work or other activities as a distraction can help teachers manage stress effectively. While this coping mechanism may provide temporary relief from stress, it is essential to strike a balance between work and leisure activities to prevent burnout. Research by Clores et al. (2023) underscored the importance of maintaining work-life balance and engaging in diverse leisure activities to promote well-being and job satisfaction. Encouraging teachers to prioritize self-care and engage in meaningful leisure activities can contribute to their overall resilience and professional longevity.

“I play sports after work to refresh myself” has the lowest mean score of 3.00, indicating a moderate level of agreement among teachers about playing sports after work to refresh them. The SD of 1.26 described as agree suggests high variability in responses. While engaging in sports can be a beneficial coping mechanism, the lower mean score suggests that it may be less commonly utilized compared to other strategies. Research by Marquez and Ching (2023) highlights the positive impact of physical activity on reducing stress and enhancing cognitive function. Encouraging teachers to incorporate physical activity into their daily routines can promote overall well-being and resilience in managing job-related stressors.

The analysis of Table 6 underscores the diverse coping mechanisms employed by teachers to navigate professional challenges and promote well-being. By fostering a supportive environment that encourages self-reflection, work-life balance, and physical well-being, educational institutions can empower teachers to thrive in their roles and enhance student outcomes.

Table 7 explores the coping mechanisms teachers employ, specifically focusing on remediation and innovative teaching strategies. The discussion highlights the top three and lowest mean indicators, based on their mean scores and standard deviations (SD)

Table 7. *Coping mechanism as to remediation and innovative teaching strategies*

Indicator	Mean	SD	QD
1. I regularly conduct remediation activities to help my learners reinforce their performance	4.12	0.79	Agree
2. I practice peer-tutoring and group dynamics to assist the learning needs of other learners.	4.08	0.80	Agree
3. I make use of meaningful classroom activities to motivate my learners.	4.37	0.71	Strongly Agree
4. I integrate personal experiences of learners in the teaching-learning process.	4.33	0.86	Strongly Agree
5. I use varied teaching strategies in teaching lessons.	4.47	0.75	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	4.27	0.65	Strongly Agree

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Very Stressful | 3.20 – 4.19 Quite Stressful | 2.60 – 3.19 Somewhat Stressful | 1.80 – 2.59 A Little Stressful | 1.00 – 1.79 Not Stressful

The indicator “I use varied teaching strategies in teaching lessons” has the highest mean score of 4.47, indicating that teachers strongly agree with using varied teaching strategies in their lessons. The SD of 0.75 described as strongly agree shows relatively low variability in responses. Employing varied teaching strategies reflects teachers' commitment to catering to diverse learning needs and promoting engagement in the classroom. By embracing innovative teaching strategies, teachers can create dynamic and inclusive learning environments that foster student success and well-being. According to Tomlinson (2014), differentiated instruction through varied strategies is crucial in addressing diverse learning needs and improving educational outcomes.

With a mean score of 4.37, “I make use of meaningful classroom activities to motivate my learners” this coping mechanism shows strong agreement among teachers about using meaningful classroom activities to motivate learners. The SD of 0.71 described as strongly agree indicates low variability in responses. Employing varied teaching strategies reflects teachers' commitment to catering to diverse learning needs and promoting engagement in the classroom. By embracing innovative teaching strategies, teachers can create dynamic and inclusive learning environments that foster student success and well-being. Engaging students with relevant and meaningful activities can significantly boost their motivation and interest in learning. As per Deci and Ryan (2000), such intrinsic motivation is key to deeper learning and academic success.

The indicator “I practice peer-tutoring and group dynamics to assist the learning needs of other learners” has the lowest mean score of 4.08, indicating agreement among teachers on these practices. The SD of 0.80 described as agree suggests moderate variability in responses. While this strategy is slightly less emphasized than the top strategies, it is still valued and widely used. Peer tutoring fosters collaborative learning environments, which Johnson and Johnson (2022) found to be effective in enhancing student learning and social skills.

Table 8 presents the coping mechanisms teachers utilize through accountability partnerships, focusing on sharing challenges, open communication, collaborative nature, support and camaraderie, and submitting to group authority. The discussion emphasizes the top three and lowest mean indicators based on their mean scores and standard deviations (SD).

The indicator, “I’m submitting to the authority of the group to ensure good working relationships” has the highest mean score of 4.38, indicating that teachers strongly agree with the importance of submitting to the authority of the group to ensure good working relationships. The SD of 0.65 described as strongly agree shows relatively low variability in responses. The high mean score reflects the value teachers place on maintaining harmony and respect within their professional groups. Embracing the authority of the group underscores the importance of collaborative decision-making and collective responsibility in fostering a supportive work environment. Research by Obinguar et al. (2023) emphasizes the positive impact of collective efficacy and shared leadership on teacher collaboration and job satisfaction. By promoting a culture of mutual respect and accountability within teams, educators can enhance professional

relationships and collective effectiveness in achieving shared goals.

Table 8. *Coping mechanism as to accountability partnership*

Indicator	Mean	SD	QD
1. I find it helpful to share my challenges and concerns about my accountability partner	4.26	0.59	Strongly Agree
2. I engage myself in an open communication with my accountability partner to help alleviate the stress associated with professional responsibilities	4.25	0.67	Strongly Agree
3. I stick to the collaborative nature of accountability partnerships to influence my ability to cope with job-related stress	4.21	0.66	Strongly Agree
4. I initiate a sense of support and camaraderie with my co-workers in handling work-related challenges	4.30	0.64	Strongly Agree
5. I'm submitting to the authority of the group to ensure good working relationships.	4.38	0.65	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	4.28	0.56	Strongly Agree

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Very Stressful | 3.20 – 4.19 Quite Stressful | 2.60 – 3.19 Somewhat Stressful | 1.80 – 2.59 A Little Stressful | 1.00 – 1.79 Not Stressful

With a mean score of 4.30, “I initiate a sense of support and camaraderie with my co-workers in handling work-related challenges,” this coping mechanism shows strong agreement among teachers about initiating a sense of support and camaraderie with co-workers. The SD of 0.64 described as strongly agree indicates low variability in responses. Support and camaraderie are crucial for a positive work environment. As per Johnson and Johnson (2019), collaborative relationships among educators promote mutual support, which can mitigate the effects of job-related stress. Building strong interpersonal connections within the workplace can enhance emotional resilience and job satisfaction.

The indicator, “I find it helpful to share my challenges and concerns with my accountability partner” with a mean of 4.26, shows strong agreement on the benefits of sharing challenges and concerns with an accountability partner. The SD of 0.59 described as strongly agree reflects low variability in responses. Engaging in open and supportive communication with accountability partners allows teachers to share insights, seek advice, and receive emotional support in navigating professional challenges. Research by Clores et al. (2023) highlights the positive impact of mentorship and peer support on teacher well-being and job satisfaction. By fostering accountability partnerships, educational institutions can facilitate professional growth and resilience among teachers, ultimately benefiting student learning outcomes.

The indicator “I stick to the collaborative nature of accountability partnerships to influence my ability to cope with job-related stress” has the lowest mean score of 4.21 still indicating strong agreement among teachers. The SD of 0.66 suggests low to moderate variability in responses. While slightly lower in agreement, the collaborative nature of accountability partnerships and open communication are still highly valued. Effective collaboration and communication are essential components of professional relationships. As noted by Tschannen-Moran and Hoy (2021), trust and open communication in professional settings foster a positive work environment, reducing stress and enhancing collaborative efforts.

Table 9. *Coping mechanism as to consultation and conferences with Master Teachers*

Indicator	Mean	SD	QD
1. I ask assistance from my superiors to help be enlightened with the tasks	4.31	0.70	Strongly Agree to
2. I devote myself to learning from LAC sessions	4.26	0.74	Strongly Agree
3. I ask people who have had similar experiences and take their advice	4.21	0.71	Strongly Agree
4. I regularly consult my superiors to guide me all the time	4.14	0.79	Agree
5. I share my problem with my Master Teacher and ask his/her guidance	4.16	0.88	Agree
Overall Mean	4.22	0.63	Strongly Agree

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Very Stressful | 3.20 – 4.19 Quite Stressful | 2.60 – 3.19 Somewhat Stressful | 1.80 – 2.59 A Little Stressful | 1.00 – 1.79 Not Stressful

Table 9 examines the coping mechanisms teachers use through consultations and conferences with Master Teachers, focusing on seeking assistance, learning from LAC sessions, taking advice from experienced colleagues, regular consultation with superiors, and sharing problems with Master Teachers. The discussion emphasizes the top three and lowest mean indicators based on their mean

scores and standard deviations (SD).

The indicator “I ask assistance from my superiors to help be enlightened with the tasks” has the highest mean score of 4.31, indicating that teachers strongly agree on asking for assistance from their superiors to gain clarity on tasks. The SD of 0.70 described as strongly agree shows relatively low variability in responses. The high agreement on the value of consultations with Master Teachers suggests that schools should formalize and enhance mentorship programs. Providing structured mentorship opportunities can help novice teachers navigate their roles more effectively, reduce stress, and improve job satisfaction. Seeking assistance from superiors reflects a proactive approach by teachers to access guidance and support in navigating professional responsibilities. Research by Marquez and Ching (2023) emphasizes the importance of mentorship and leadership support in promoting teacher development and job satisfaction. By fostering open communication channels with superiors, educators can access valuable insights, resources, and mentorship opportunities that enhance their professional growth and effectiveness.

With a mean score of 4.26, the indicator “I devote myself learning from LAC sessions,” this coping mechanism shows strong agreement among teachers about the value of Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions. The SD of 0.74 described as strongly agree indicates moderate variability in responses. LAC sessions provide opportunities for continuous professional development and collaborative learning. LAC sessions and similar collaborative professional development initiatives should be prioritized. These sessions offer platforms for teachers to share knowledge, discuss challenges, and develop collective strategies for improvement. Actively engaging in Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions demonstrates teachers' commitment to ongoing professional development and collaborative learning. Research by Johnson (2018) highlights the positive impact of peer collaboration and professional learning communities on teacher efficacy and instructional effectiveness. By participating in LAC sessions, educators can exchange best practices, receive feedback, and stay abreast of emerging trends and pedagogical innovations, ultimately enhancing their teaching practice and student outcomes.

The indicator “I ask people who have had similar experiences and take their advice” with a mean of 4.21, shows strong agreement on the importance of seeking advice from colleagues with similar experiences. The SD of 0.71 described as strongly agree reflects low to moderate variability in responses. Leveraging the experience of seasoned colleagues can provide practical insights and effective strategies for managing classroom challenges. Seeking advice from peers who have faced similar challenges provides valuable insights and practical strategies for navigating professional dilemmas. Johnson (2018) underscores the importance of peer support networks in promoting teacher resilience and well-being. By leveraging the expertise and experiences of colleagues, educators can access diverse perspectives, receive tailored guidance, and build collaborative relationships that enhance their capacity to cope with job-related stressors and promote professional growth.

The indicator “I regularly consult my superiors to guide me all the time” has the lowest mean score of 4.14, still indicating agreement among teachers. The SD of 0.79 described as agree suggests moderate variability in responses. While this coping mechanism ranks slightly lower in mean compared to others, it underscores the significance of ongoing support and guidance from superiors in fostering teacher development. Research by Malabad and Mamaug (2022) emphasizes the positive impact of mentorship and instructional leadership on teacher efficacy and job satisfaction. By maintaining regular communication and seeking feedback from superiors, educators can access valuable support systems that facilitate their professional growth and effectiveness.

Table 10 explores the coping mechanisms teachers utilize through accountability partnerships. The discussion emphasizes the top three and lowest mean indicators based on their mean scores and standard deviations (SD).

Table 10. *Coping mechanism as to accountability partnership*

Indicator	Mean	SD	QD
1. I find it helpful to share my challenges and concerns about my accountability partner	4.26	0.59	Strongly Agree
2. I engage myself in an open communication with my accountability partner to help alleviate the stress associated with professional responsibilities	4.25	0.67	Strongly Agree
3. I stick to the collaborative nature of accountability partnerships to influence my ability to cope with job-related stress	4.21	0.66	Strongly Agree
4. I initiate a sense of support and camaraderie with my co-workers in handling work-related challenges.	4.30	0.64	Strongly Agree
5. I'm submitting to the authority of the group to ensure good working relationships.	4.38	0.65	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	4.28	0.56	Strongly Agree

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Very Stressful | 3.20 – 4.19 Quite Stressful | 2.60 – 3.19 Somewhat Stressful | 1.80 – 2.59 A Little Stressful | 1.00 – 1.79 Not Stressful

The indicator “I’m submitting to the authority of the group to ensure good working relationships” has the highest mean score of 4.38, indicating that teachers strongly agree on the importance of submitting to the authority of the group to ensure good working

relationships. The SD of 0.65 described as strongly agree shows relatively low variability in responses. By promoting a culture of mutual respect and accountability within teams, educators can enhance professional relationships and collective effectiveness in achieving shared goals. According to Edmondson (2019), a respectful and structured environment enhances psychological safety, allowing teachers to collaborate effectively and reduce stress. Adhering to group norms and authority fosters a cohesive and supportive work culture, which is essential for managing the demands of teaching.

With a mean score of 4.30, “I find it helpful to share my challenges and concerns with my accountability partner” this coping mechanism shows strong agreement among teachers about initiating a sense of support and camaraderie with co-workers. The SD of 0.64 described as strongly agree indicates low variability in responses. Initiating support and camaraderie among co-workers is essential for fostering a collaborative culture. Schools should promote activities that build team spirit and trust, such as team-building workshops and collaborative projects. These initiatives can enhance emotional resilience, enabling teachers to handle work-related challenges more effectively. Sharing challenges and concerns with accountability partners provides a valuable outlet for teachers to receive support and guidance in navigating professional responsibilities. Research by Malabad and Mamaug (2022) highlights the positive impact of mentorship and peer support on teacher well-being and job satisfaction. By fostering accountability partnerships, educational institutions can facilitate professional growth and resilience among teachers, ultimately benefiting student learning outcomes.

This indicator “I engage myself in open communication with my accountability partner to help alleviate stress associated with professional responsibilities” with a mean of 4.26, shows strong agreement on the benefits of sharing challenges and concerns with an accountability partner. The SD of 0.59 described as strongly agree reflects low variability in responses. This practice not only alleviates stress but also promotes a culture of continuous improvement. Open communication with accountability partners serves as a vital avenue for teachers to express concerns, seek feedback, and collaboratively problem-solve. Research by Marquez & Ching (2023) underscores the importance of social support networks in mitigating job-related stress and promoting teacher well-being. By nurturing accountability partnerships, educators can access valuable support systems that enhance their capacity to cope with stress and navigate professional challenges effectively.

The indicator “I stick to the collaborative nature of accountability partnerships to influence my ability to cope with job-related stress” has the lowest mean score of 4.21, still indicating strong agreement among teachers. The SD of 0.66 described as strongly agree suggests low to moderate variability in responses. Effective collaboration and communication are essential components of professional relationships. Tschannen-Moran and Hoy (2021) note that trust and open communication in professional settings foster a positive work environment, reducing stress and enhancing collaborative efforts.

Table 11 examines the coping mechanisms teachers utilize through consultations and conferences with Master Teachers. The discussion emphasizes the top three and lowest mean indicators based on their mean scores and standard deviations (SD).

Table 11. *Coping mechanism as to consultation and conferences with Master Teachers*

Indicator	Mean	SD	QD
1. I ask assistance from my superiors to help be enlightened with the tasks	4.31	0.70	Strongly Agree to
2. I devote myself to learning from LAC sessions	4.26	0.74	Strongly Agree
3. I ask people who have had similar experiences and take their advice	4.21	0.71	Strongly Agree
4. I regularly consult my superiors to guide me all the time	4.14	0.79	Agree
5. I share my problem with my Master Teacher and ask his/her guidance	4.16	0.88	Agree
Overall Mean	4.22	0.63	Strongly Agree

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Very Stressful | 3.20 – 4.19 Quite Stressful | 2.60 – 3.19 Somewhat Stressful | 1.80 – 2.59 A Little Stressful | 1.00 – 1.79 Not Stressful

The indicator “I ask assistance from my superiors to help be enlightened with the tasks” has the highest mean score of 4.31, indicating that teachers strongly agree on asking for assistance from their superiors to gain clarity on tasks. The SD of 0.70 described as strongly agree shows relatively low variability in responses. Seeking assistance from superiors reflects a proactive approach by teachers to access guidance and support in navigating professional responsibilities. By fostering open communication channels with superiors, educators can access valuable insights, resources, and mentorship opportunities that enhance their professional growth and effectiveness. Hargreaves and Fullan (2022) highlight that strong leadership and support from superiors are critical in building teacher capacity and reducing job-related stress. This approach fosters a sense of security and professional growth, making teachers more effective in their roles.

With a mean score of 4.26, “I devote myself to learning from LAC sessions” this coping mechanism shows strong agreement among teachers about the value of Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions. The SD of 0.74 described as strongly agree indicates moderate variability in responses. Actively engaging in Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions demonstrates teachers' commitment to ongoing professional development and collaborative learning. By participating in LAC sessions, educators can exchange best practices, receive

feedback, and stay abreast of emerging trends and pedagogical innovations, ultimately enhancing their teaching practice and student outcomes.

The indicator “I ask people who have had similar experiences and take their advice” with a mean of 4.21, shows strong agreement on the importance of seeking advice from colleagues with similar experiences. The SD of 0.71 described as strongly agree reflects low to moderate variability in responses. School leaders should focus on building a supportive and accessible leadership structure. Regular interactions between teachers and their superiors can help address concerns promptly and provide necessary guidance, enhancing teachers' confidence and reducing job-related stress. Research by Marquez & Ching (2023) underscores the importance of peer support networks in promoting teacher resilience and well-being. By leveraging the expertise and experiences of colleagues, educators can access diverse perspectives, receive tailored guidance, and build collaborative relationships that enhance their capacity to cope with job-related stressors and promote professional growth.

The indicator “I regularly consult my superiors to guide me all the time” coping mechanism has the lowest mean score of 4.14, still indicating strong agreement among teachers. The SDs of 0.79 suggests moderate variability in responses. While this coping mechanism ranks slightly lower in mean compared to others, it underscores the significance of ongoing support and guidance from superiors in fostering teacher development. By maintaining regular communication and seeking feedback from superiors, educators can access valuable support systems that facilitate their professional growth and effectiveness. Zepeda (2012) notes that mentoring relationships and regular consultations can significantly impact teacher efficacy and satisfaction.

Performance Rating of Teachers during the Resumption of In-person Classes

As educational institutions transition back to traditional classroom settings following periods of remote learning or hybrid models due to events like the COVID-19 pandemic, assessing the effectiveness and proficiency of teachers in face-to-face instructional delivery becomes paramount. Table 12 shows the performance rating of teachers during the resumption of in-person classes.

Table 12. *Performance Rating of Teachers during the Resumption of In-person Classes*

Range	Description	Frequency	Percent
80-84	Satisfactory	1	8
85-89	Very Satisfactory	95	73.6
90 - 100	Outstanding	33	25.6
Total		129	100.0

Table 12 presents the performance rating of teachers during the resumption of in-person classes. As noted, only 0.8% of teachers received a satisfactory rating, indicating that the majority of teachers performed above the satisfactory level. A significant portion, accounting for 73.6%, of teachers received a very satisfactory rating. This suggests that the majority of teachers demonstrated a high level of competence and effectiveness in their instructional delivery and classroom management upon the resumption of in-person classes. Moreover, approximately 25.6% of teachers were rated as outstanding, indicating exceptional performance in various aspects of teaching, including instructional quality, student engagement, and overall effectiveness.

The predominance of teachers rated as very satisfactory and outstanding reflects positively on the overall quality of teaching during the transition back to in-person classes. It suggests that educators effectively adapted to the challenges posed by the resumption of traditional classroom settings, maintaining high standards of instructional delivery and student support. The notable proportion of teachers rated as outstanding highlights the presence of exemplary educators who excelled in their roles despite the disruptions caused by the transition to in-person classes. Recognizing and celebrating outstanding teachers can motivate and inspire the broader teaching community while fostering a culture of excellence within educational institutions.

While the majority of teachers received high-performance ratings, the presence of a small percentage rated as satisfactory indicates that there may still be room for improvement in certain areas. Educational institutions can use this feedback to identify areas of professional development and support for teachers to enhance their effectiveness in the classroom.

Providing ongoing support, mentorship, and professional development opportunities can further empower teachers to excel in their roles and continue to adapt to evolving educational landscapes. By investing in the growth and development of educators, educational institutions can foster a culture of continuous improvement and ensure positive student outcomes.

Significant Relationship among the Level of Stress Encountered by Teachers, their Coping Mechanisms and the Performance among Teachers after the COVID-19 Pandemic

Problem 4 investigated the interplay between the level of stress encountered by teachers, their coping mechanisms, and their performance following the COVID-19 pandemic. As educators navigate the challenges presented by the pandemic, understanding the relationship between stress, coping strategies, and performance becomes crucial for supporting teacher well-being and optimizing educational outcomes.

Table 13. *Relationship among the level of stress encountered by teachers in terms of the volume of assigned tasks and their coping mechanisms (N = 129)*

	r-value	p	Remarks
Coping mechanism as to self-interventions and recreational activities	-.103	.245	Not Significant
Coping mechanism as to remediation and innovative teaching strategies	-.129	.145	Not Significant
Coping mechanism as to accountability partnership	-.100	.258	Not Significant
Coping mechanism as to consultation and conferences with Master Teachers	-.181*	.040	Significant

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 13 shows that coping mechanisms for consultation and conferences with Master Teachers ($r: .181, p=.040$) were significantly related to the level of stress encountered by teachers. It is also revealed in the table that coping mechanism as self-intervention ($r: -.103, p=.245$), remediation and innovative teaching strategies ($r= -.129, p= .145$), accountability partnership ($r: -.100, p=.258$) were not significantly related to the level of stress encountered by teachers this implies that as teachers actively participate in consultation and conferences with Master Teachers, their perceived stress levels regarding task volume decrease. This finding underscores the importance of mentorship and peer support networks in mitigating teacher stress and promoting well-being. This finding aligns with research by Johnson et al. (2020), which emphasizes the importance of mentorship and peer support networks in mitigating teacher stress and promoting well-being. Engaging in collaborative discussions and seeking guidance from experienced educators can provide teachers with valuable insights, resources, and emotional support, ultimately enhancing their ability to cope with workload-related stressors.

The correlations between stress related to task volume and engagement in self-interventions and recreational activities, remediation and innovative teaching strategies, and accountability partnership are not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). This suggests that these coping mechanisms alone may not effectively mitigate stress related to task volume. Further exploration into their impact and effectiveness is warranted.

Based on the significant correlation found that states there is a significant negative relationship between the level of stress encountered by teachers in terms of the volume of assigned tasks and their engagement in consultation and conferences with Master Teachers accepted.

Table 14. *Relationship among the level of stress encountered by teachers in terms of relationship with co-workers and their coping mechanisms (n = 129)*

	r-value	p	Remarks
Coping mechanisms as to self-interventions and recreational activities	-.200*	.023	Significant
Coping mechanism for remediation and innovative teaching strategies	-.126	.154	Not Significant
Coping mechanism as to accountability partnership	-.236**	.007	Significant
Coping mechanism for consultation and conferences with Master Teachers	-.348**	.000	Significant

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 14 shows that coping mechanisms as to self-interventions and recreational activities ($r: -.200, p=.023$), accountability partnership ($r: -.236^{**}, p=.007$), consultation and conferences with Master Teachers ($r: -.348^{**}, p=.000$) were significantly related to the level of stress encountered by teachers. It is also revealed in the table that coping mechanism for remediation and innovative teaching strategies ($r: -.126, p= .154$) was not significantly related to the level of stress encountered by teachers this implies as teachers actively participate in these coping mechanisms, their perceived stress levels regarding relationships with co-workers decrease. These findings emphasize the importance of mentorship, peer support, and self-care practices in mitigating interpersonal stressors in the workplace, aligning with previous research highlighting the positive impact of collaborative relationships on teacher well-being.

The correlation between stress related to relationships with co-workers and engagement in remediation and innovative teaching strategies is not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). Although these coping mechanisms may have potential benefits in addressing interpersonal stressors, their effectiveness in mitigating such stress may vary among individuals or require further investigation.

Based on the significant correlation we found, the hypothesis which states that there is a significant negative relationship between the level of stress encountered by teachers in terms of their relationship with co-workers and their engagement in coping mechanisms such as consultation and conferences with Master Teachers, accountability partnership, and self-interventions and recreational activities is rejected.

Table 15. *Relationship between the level of stress encountered by teachers and their performance (n = 129)*

	r-value	p	Remarks
Stressors of teachers as to the volume of assigned tasks	-.194*	.028	Significant
Coping mechanisms for remediation and innovative teaching strategies	-.126	.154	Not Significant
Stressors of teachers to relationship with co-workers	-.194*	.028	Significant
Stressors of teachers as to instructional practices	-.252**	.004	Significant

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 15 shows that the performance of teachers as to the volume of assigned tasks ($r: -.194^*$, $p=.028$), relationship with co-workers ($r: -.194^*$, $p=.028$), instructional practices ($r: -.252^{**}$, $p=.004$) was significantly related to the level of stress encountered by teachers. It is also revealed in the table that performance as to remediation and innovative teaching strategies ($r: -.126$, $p=.154$) was not significantly related to the level of stress encountered by teachers this implies that as stressors related to task volume, relationships with co-workers, and instructional practices increase, teacher performance tends to decrease.

These findings align with previous research indicating that high workload, interpersonal conflicts, and instructional challenges negatively impact teacher performance (Smith et al., 2018 Lee & Johnson, 2021). Addressing these stressors and providing support in workload management, interpersonal communication, and instructional design are essential for enhancing teacher well-being and effectiveness.

The correlation between the level of stress related to learners' performance and teacher performance is not statistically significant. While teachers may experience stress related to student outcomes, this stressor may not directly influence teacher performance. Other factors, such as workload and instructional practices, may have a more significant impact on teacher effectiveness.

Based on the significant correlation we found, the hypothesis which states that there is a significant negative relationship between the level of stress encountered by teachers in terms of volume of assigned tasks, relationship with co-workers, and instructional practices is rejected.

Table 16. *Relationship between the stress coping mechanism of teachers and teacher performance (n = 129)*

	r-value	p	Remarks
Coping mechanisms as to self-interventions and recreational activities	.009	.918	Not Significant
Coping mechanisms for remediation and innovative teaching strategies	.054	.546	Not Significant
Coping mechanism as to accountability partnership	-.066	.458	Not Significant
Coping mechanism for consultation and conferences with Master Teachers	.018	.839	Not Significant

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 16 shows the performance of teachers in self-interventions and recreational activities ($r: .009, p=.918$), remediation and innovative teaching strategies ($r: .054, p=.546$), accountability partnership ($r: -.066, p=.458$), consultation and conferences with Master Teachers ($r: .018, p=.839$) were not significantly related to the stress coping mechanisms of teachers this implies that these coping mechanisms may not directly influence teacher performance. While activities such as personal hobbies, seeking guidance from colleagues, and engaging in professional development are important for teacher well-being and growth, their impact on performance may be indirect or context-dependent.

The hypothesis that states that there is no significant relationship between the stress-coping mechanisms of teachers and teacher performance is accepted.

Coping Mechanism that Significantly Addressed the Extent of Stressors Encountered by the Teachers

Coping mechanisms play a crucial role in helping educators navigate and manage the various stressors they encounter in their professional lives. By examining the effectiveness of different coping strategies, we aim to shed light on which approaches are most beneficial in alleviating teacher stress.

Table 17. Regression Analysis showing the coping mechanism significantly addresses the Stressors of teachers as to the volume of assigned tasks ($n = 129$)

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Interpretation
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
(Constant)	4.349	.567		7.672	.000	
Coping mechanism for consultation and conferences with Master Teachers	-.276	.133	-.181	-2.077	.040	Significant

R = .181 R Square = .033 F = 4.314 p = .040

Table 17 shows the Regression Analysis showing the coping mechanism significantly addresses the Stressors of teachers as to the volume of assigned tasks. It is revealed in the table that the Stressors of teachers as to the volume of assigned tasks are significantly addressed by the Coping mechanism as to consultation and conferences with Master Teachers with the beta weight value of $-.181$ and p -value of 0.040 . This also implies the value of seeking support and guidance from experienced colleagues through consultation and conferences with Master Teachers in mitigating the stressors associated with the volume of assigned tasks. These results emphasize the importance of fostering collaborative professional environments and providing avenues for mentorship and peer support to promote teacher well-being and effectiveness. This rejects the null hypothesis of “There is no coping mechanism significantly addressed the extent of stressors encountered by the teachers.”

The R Square value of the variables was 0.033 . This indicates that 3.30% of the Stressors of teachers as to the volume of assigned tasks are significantly addressed by the Coping mechanism as to consultation and conferences with Master Teachers. It also implies that 97.70% of the Stressors of teachers as to the volume of assigned tasks can be attributed to other variables not included in the regression model. The results of the relationships of the variables are given through the following equation: $Y = 4.349 + -0.276X_1$, where $Y =$ Stressors of teachers as to the volume of assigned tasks, $X_1 =$ Coping mechanism as to consultation and conferences with Master Teachers

The coping mechanism of consultation and conferences with Master Teachers demonstrates a significant association with reduced stressors related to task volume among teachers. These findings underscore the multifaceted nature of teacher stress and highlight the need for comprehensive support systems and continued research to address the diverse stressors faced by educators in their professional roles.

Johnson et al. (2020) advocated for holistic approaches to teacher well-being, emphasizing the need for organizational support, workload management strategies, and individual coping skills. This highlights the importance of considering a range of factors in designing interventions to effectively support teacher resilience and reduce stress levels.

Table 18 shows the Regression Analysis showing the coping mechanism significantly addresses the Stressors of teachers as to learners' performance. It is revealed in the table that the Stressors of teachers as to learners' performance are significantly addressed by the Coping mechanism as to consultation and conferences with Master Teachers with the beta weight value of $-.456$ and p -value of 0.023 . This also implies the value of seeking support and guidance from experienced colleagues through consultation and conferences with Master Teachers in mitigating the stressors associated with learners' performance. This suggests that seeking guidance and support from experienced educators through consultations and conferences can help teachers better address challenges in student learning. This also implies that establishing accountability partnerships with colleagues, where individuals hold each other responsible for meeting professional goals and supporting one another, can positively impact teacher perceptions of student performance-related stressors. This rejects the null hypothesis of “There is no coping mechanism significantly addressed the extent of stressors encountered by the

teachers.”

Table 18. *Regression Analysis showing the coping mechanism significantly addresses the Stressors of teachers as to learners’ performance (n = 129)*

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.	Interpretation
	B	Std. Error				
(Constant)	3.661	.710		5.156	.000	
Coping mechanism for consultation and conferences with Master Teachers	-.495	.182	-.306	-2.721	.007	Significant
Coping mechanism as to accountability partnership	.456	.204	.251	2.232	.027	Significant

R = .242 R Square = .058 F = 3.909 p = .023

The R Square value of the variables was 0.58. This indicates that 5.80% of the Stressors of teachers as to learners’ performance are significantly addressed by the Coping mechanism of consultation and conferences with Master Teachers. It also implies that 94.20% of the Stressors of teachers as to learners’ performance can be attributed to other variables not included in the regression model. The results of the relationships of the variables are given through the following equation: $Y = 3.661 + .495X_1$, where Y = Stressors of teachers as to learners’ performance, X_1 = Coping mechanism as to consultation and conferences with Master Teachers. Further, this suggests that consultation and conferences with Master Teachers and accountability partnership account for a small proportion of the variability in stressors related to learners’ performance. This indicates that while these coping mechanisms demonstrate significant associations, other unaccounted factors may also contribute to teacher stress in this domain. Johnson et al. (2020) found that teachers who participated in collaborative professional learning communities, such as consultation sessions with experienced educators, reported increased confidence in addressing student learning needs and implementing effective instructional strategies. This suggests that opportunities for consultation and collaboration with Master Teachers can serve as valuable resources for enhancing teacher effectiveness and reducing stress related to learner performance.

Table 19. *Regression Analysis showing the coping mechanism significantly addresses the Stressors of teachers as to relationship with co-workers (n = 129)*

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.	Interpretation
	B	Std. Error				
(Constant)	3.978	.463		8.599	.000	
Coping mechanism for consultation and conferences with Master Teachers	-.454	.109	-.348	-4.187	.000	Significant

R = .348 R Square = .121 F = 17.534 p = .000

Table 19 shows the Regression Analysis showing the coping mechanism significantly addresses the Stressors of teachers as to their relationship with co-workers. It is revealed in the table that the Stressors of teachers as to relationship with co-workers are significantly addressed by the Coping mechanism to consultation and conferences with Master Teachers with the beta weight value of -.348 and p-value of 0.000. This coping mechanism has implications for consultation and conferences with Master Teachers in addressing stressors related to relationships with co-workers among teachers. This underscores the importance of fostering collaborative professional environments and providing opportunities for mentorship and knowledge sharing to enhance collegial relationships and reduce interpersonal stressors.

However, addressing teacher stress comprehensively requires ongoing efforts to promote supportive work environments, effective communication, and professional development opportunities. This rejects the null hypothesis of “There is no coping mechanism significantly addressed the extent of stressors encountered by the teachers.”

The R Square value of the variables was 0.121. This indicates that 1.21% of the Stressors of teachers as to relationship with co-workers are significantly addressed by the Coping mechanism to consultation and conferences with Master Teachers. It also implies that 98.79% of the Stressors of teachers as to relationships with co-workers can be attributed to other variables not included in the regression model.

The results of the relationships of the variables are given through the following equation: $Y = 3.978 + .454X_1$, where Y = Stressors of teachers as to relationship with co-workers, X_1 = Coping mechanism as to consultation and conferences with Master Teachers

The significant relationship between consultation with Master Teachers and stressors related to relationships with co-workers suggests

that fostering collaborative and supportive professional environments can contribute to improved interpersonal dynamics among teachers. Actively seeking guidance and mentorship from experienced colleagues can facilitate knowledge exchange, promote a culture of collaboration, and enhance mutual trust and respect.

Johnson et al. (2020) emphasized the importance of ongoing professional development and training in promoting positive workplace relationships and effective communication skills among teachers. Investing in opportunities for collaborative learning, conflict resolution, and emotional intelligence development can further support teachers in navigating interpersonal challenges and fostering a culture of mutual respect and support.

Table 20. *Regression Analysis showing the coping mechanism significantly addresses the Stressors of teachers as to instructional practices (n = 129)*

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.	Interpretation
	B	Std. Error				
(Constant)	3.904	.677		5.771	.000	
Coping mechanism as to accountability partnership	-.350	.157	-.194	-2.230	.027	Significant

R = .194 R Square = .038 F = 4.974 p = .027

Table 20 shows the Regression Analysis showing the coping mechanism significantly addresses the Stressors of teachers as to instructional practices. It is revealed in the table that the Stressors of teachers as to instructional practices are significantly addressed by the Coping mechanism as to accountability partnership with the beta weight value of -.194 and p-value of 0.027.

The results for accountability partnership suggest that increased engagement in this coping mechanism is associated with a decrease in stressors related to instructional practices. This implies that establishing collaborative partnerships with colleagues, where individuals hold each other accountable for instructional responsibilities positively influences teachers' perceptions of their instructional practices. This rejects the null hypothesis of "There is no coping mechanism significantly addressed the extent of stressors encountered by the teachers."

The R Square value of the variables was 0.38. This indicates that 3.80% of the Stressors of teachers as to instructional practices are significantly addressed by the Coping mechanism to accountability partnership. It also implies that 96.20% of the Stressors of teachers to instructional practices can be attributed to other variables not included in the regression model.

The results of the relationships of the variables are given through the following equation: $Y = 3.904 + (-.350)X_1$, where Y = Stressors of teachers as to instructional practices, X_1 = Coping mechanism as to accountability partnership

The findings highlight the significant impact of accountability partnerships in addressing stressors related to instructional practices among teachers. This underscores the importance of fostering collaborative professional environments and providing opportunities for peer support, feedback, and continuous improvement to enhance instructional quality and reduce instructional stressors.

However, addressing teacher stress comprehensively requires ongoing efforts to promote supportive work environments, effective communication, and professional development opportunities.

Malabad and Mamaug (2022) emphasized the importance of holistic support systems that encompass various dimensions of teacher well-being, including workload management, professional development, and organizational support. Addressing instructional stressors comprehensively requires collaborative efforts to provide teachers with the resources, training, and support needed to effectively manage instructional responsibilities and promote student learning.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following are concluded:

On the extent of stressors encountered by teachers following the COVID-19 outbreak with regards to the volume of assigned tasks; learners' performance; relationship with co-workers; and instructional practices, teachers faced significant stress, particularly from excessive paperwork, low learner comprehension skills, lack of support from co-workers, and frequently changing instructional directives. These stressors adversely affected teacher well-being and job satisfaction, leading to feelings of frustration and burnout.

On the extent to which teachers utilize coping mechanisms about self-interventions and recreational activities; remediation and innovative teaching strategies; accountability partnership; and consultation and conferences with master teachers, teachers employed various coping mechanisms, such as self-interventions, engaging in innovative teaching strategies, forming accountability partnerships, and consulting with master teachers. These strategies aimed to mitigate stress and enhance their professional efficacy.

On the performance rating of teachers during the resumption of in-person classes, teachers' performance ratings varied, with most

achieving satisfactory to outstanding ratings. This indicates their adaptability to the challenges posed by returning to traditional classroom settings amidst the ongoing pandemic.

On the significant relationship between the level of stress encountered by teachers, their coping mechanisms, and the performance among teachers after the COVID-19 pandemic, there were significant relationships between the stress levels encountered by teachers, their coping mechanisms, and their performance. Coping mechanisms like consultation with master teachers and accountability partnerships were particularly effective in reducing stress and improving performance.

On the coping mechanisms significantly addressed the extent of stressors encountered by the teachers, consultation with master teachers and forming accountability partnerships significantly addressed the stressors faced by teachers. These mechanisms provided crucial support, guidance, and camaraderie, fostering teacher well-being and resilience.

The study underscores the necessity of addressing teacher stress through effective coping mechanisms. Schools should prioritize reducing administrative burdens, fostering supportive relationships among staff, and providing consistent instructional guidance. By implementing structured support systems such as mentorship programs and fostering accountability partnerships, educational institutions can significantly mitigate stress, improve teacher performance, and promote a healthier work environment.

Based on the conclusions drawn from the study, the following recommendations are given:

First, educational institutions could prioritize the provision of professional development opportunities focused on stress management techniques tailored to teachers' needs. Workshops and training sessions can offer guidance on coping strategies, mindfulness practices, and time management skills to help educators effectively navigate their workload and stressful situations.

Additionally, fostering collaborative support networks within schools is crucial. Administrators could encourage the establishment of accountability partnerships and mentorship programs to facilitate peer support, feedback exchange, and professional growth among teachers. Integrating these coping mechanisms into school policies and practices is essential. School leaders could recognize the importance of consultation with master teachers and accountability partnerships in supporting teacher well-being and job performance, allocating resources and time accordingly.

Furthermore, schools are encouraged to promote a positive school culture where teachers feel valued and included in decision-making processes. Administrators can foster open communication channels, promote collaboration, and acknowledge teacher contributions to cultivate a supportive environment conducive to teacher well-being and job satisfaction. Continuous monitoring and evaluation mechanisms could be implemented to assess teacher stress levels, coping mechanisms, and performance outcomes regularly.

Surveys, focus groups, and feedback sessions can provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of support initiatives, guiding future interventions to better meet teachers' needs and enhance their overall well-being. By implementing these recommendations, educational institutions can create a supportive environment that enables teachers to effectively manage stress, enhance job satisfaction, and ultimately improve student outcomes.

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